

Interference and Fermions and Bosons

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Dec. 18, 2021

Interference is an important observed feature in quantum mechanics. It is often seen in terms of peaks and troughs in two slit interference or in the profile of bound state wavefunction (e.g. harmonic oscillator). In this note, we argue that interference also plays a central role in determining the two types of quantum particles which exist i.e. fermions and bosons. Whereas a wavefunction is subject to a global constraint (its integral over x is 1), a local spatial probability constraint is imposed (at each x) in the case of at least two particles built from a separable wavefunction $W_a(x_1)W_b(x_2)$. Here there are two indistinguishable particles, two allowable energy levels a and b and one wishes to know the probability of finding a particle at x_1 and one at x_2 regardless of the energy level. Let us call this $P(x_1, x_2)$. The modulus squared of the wavefunction yields probability P , so a constructed wavefunction may have the property that the interchange of x_1 and x_2 yields a phase factor. This argument is presented often although (1) suggests it should be modified, yet the conclusion that there are only fermions and bosons remains.

In this note, we consider the existence of two types of interference as the physical basis of this result. From the Schrodinger equation or from $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx) / W$ one may see that $W \rightarrow -W$ and $a(p) \rightarrow -a(p)$ is still a solution. In quantum mechanics not only do $\exp(ipx)$ terms interfere, but eigenfunctions W_n may also interfere. Given that a bound eigenfunction may be represented by W_n or $-W_n$, there exists two kinds of interference. Even in the case in which there is only one particle, one may already create two possibilities: $W_a(x) + W_b(x)$ and $W_a(x) - W_b(x)$. If one sets $a=b$, the second becomes 0 at each x . This we argue already points to the idea of fermions even though only one particle is considered. This result is due strictly to alternate phase (1, -1) interference). The idea of alternate phase interference $W_a - W_b$ also seems to be linked to a difference in wavefunction i.e. a "kind" of wavefunction representing the change in moving from energy level a to b .

Thus we try to argue that there is interference beyond the usual $\exp(ipx)$ namely an alternate phase interference which applies to eigenfunctions $W_n(x)$ and leads to the existence of fermions. Bosons occur with no alternate phase interference. These two types of particles emerge from the constraint that $P(x_1, x_2) = P(x_2, x_1)$ i.e a local spatial probability constraint.

Fermions

Fermions differ from bosons in that only one particle may occupy a specific quantum state characterized by a set of quantum numbers. The differentiating quantum number may not necessarily depend on the energy as in the case of spin up and down for a Hamiltonian which does not depend on spin interactions or have a magnetic field. A different Hamiltonian, however, may cause these quantum numbers to change the energy value. Either way, it seems that even though fermions are said to be indistinguishable, a particular fermion in a system must have a unique set of quantum numbers. This is almost as if the fermions are distinguishable (unlike bosons which may have the same set of quantum numbers) although interchanging two fermions does not change the system. As a result of a fermion having a unique set of quantum

numbers, interactions involving them are special in that one may not “scatter” into an occupied state. A question which remains, however, is: what is the physical reason for this unusual rule?

Permutations

The existence of two types of particles, fermions and bosons, seems to be based on permutations i.e. $P(x_1, x_2) = P(x_2, x_1)$. In quantum mechanics, spatial probability is based on the modulus squared of a wavefunction. If there are say two energy levels a and b, then x_1 may be part of either a or b and a similar result holds for x_2 . Thus, one forms linear combinations of two particle separable wavefunctions i.e. $W_a(x_1)W_b(x_2)$ and $W_a(x_2)W_b(x_1)$. The combination, however, must satisfy the local constraint $P(x_1, x_2) = P(x_2, x_1)$. Usually one only imposes a global constraint i.e. $W^*a(x)W_a(x)$, $W^*b(x)W_b(x)$ and $W_{\text{overall}}^*(x)W_{\text{overall}}(x)$ integrate over space to 1. The extra local constraint yields two kinds of particles, fermions and bosons. In (1) these conclusions are arrived at although the author argues that arguments usually given in standard textbooks are too simplistic.

The physical reason for resulting fermions, however, seems to be alternate phase interference i.e. $W_a(x_1)W_b(x_2) - W_a(x_2)W_b(x_1)$ which appears to be different than the usual $\exp(ipx)$ interference within a specific $W_i(x)$ eigenfunction i.e. carries an extra phase.

Interference

Interference is a main feature of a quantum particle. A free particle is represented by $\exp(ipx)$ which suggests two dimensions each with an associated probability $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. There is another probability in the picture associated with particle number i.e. there is one particle and $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$. If one adds the conditional complex probabilities $\exp(ip_1 x)$ and $\exp(ip_2 x)$, interference occurs i.e. one no longer has a fixed particle number at position x , only the integral of the modulus squared i.e. W^*W is 1. Interference we argue is based on some kind of physical mechanism associated with the two dimensional probability.

In the case of a potential $V(x)$, one has a momentum distribution $W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \sum \text{over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and a conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx) / W(x)$. It is possible to set $W \rightarrow -W$ (i.e. $a(p) \rightarrow -a(p)$), although for a single eigenstate $W_i(x)$, this does not seem to carry much importance. Using the conditional probability and energy conservation at each x one arrives at:

$$[\sum \text{over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx)] / W + V(x) = E_n \quad ((1)) \text{ (time independent Schrodinger equation)}$$

This yields a series of eigenfunction solutions $W_n(x)$ associated with discrete energies E_n . The wavefunction itself may have crests and troughs (e.g. oscillator wavefunctions) which are due to interference.

One may, however, have interference between eigenfunctions. Usually a bound particle is in a single eigenstate, but if there is a heat reservoir, one may have:

$$W(x,t) = \sum \text{over } n \ a_n(E_n) \exp(-i E_n t) W_n(x) \quad ((2))$$

If one sets $t = 0$, one may consider two special cases:

$$W(x) = W_1(x) + W_2(x) \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad W(x) = W_1(x) - W_2(x) \quad ((3b))$$

These both exhibit wavefunction interference which is a physical phenomenon already existing at the $\exp(ipx)$ level. Overall, the integral of $W^*(x)W(x)$ is 1 so one does not “lose” the particle. One may see, however, alternate phase interference appearing in ((3b)). If one sets $1=2$ then ((3b)) becomes 0. In other words, ((3b)) is a wavefunction which measures a difference in the wavefunctions of the two bound states W_1 and W_2 . It is as if it is almost associated with an excitation that exists pushing W_1 up to W_2 , although one must be careful with this analogy.

We argue that the situation of ((3a)) and ((3b)) may be extended to a two identical particle separable wavefunction case. There, one insists that $P(x_1, x_2) = P(x_2, x_1)$ so for two allowable energy states a and b , one has two wavefunctions:

$$W_a(x_1)W_b(x_2) + W_a(x_2)W_b(x_1) \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and the alternate phase} \quad W_a(x_2)W_b(x_1) - W_a(x_1)W_b(x_2) \quad ((4b))$$

Both ((4a)) and ((4b)) involve the same physical interference of $\exp(ipx)$, but there is an additional phase factor of -1 involved in the case of ((4b)). There seems to be an added interference condition i.e. the possibility of extra phases occurring in the interference of wavefunctions. If one examines ((4b)) and sets $a=b$, one obtains 0. In other words, one fermion must be in one energy state and the other in the other. Alternate phase interference does not allow for two particles with the same wavefunction as the wavefunctions interfere out of phase by π .

In other words, it seems there are two manifestations of interference. First, one has crests and troughs in two slit experiments and spatial density profiles, but secondly out of phase interference by π may give rise to the wavefunction for two identical fermions vanishing if both are in the same energy state. In the case of a single bound state, one does not have the flexibility to add arbitrary phases because the constraint ((1)) exists. For wavefunction interference, the constraint is $P(x_1, x_2) = P(x_2, x_1)$, so an alternate phase solution is consistent. In other words, the Pauli exclusion principle may be a result of interference. (It may be noted that interference in calculations accounts for an absence of electromagnetic fields in regions of space. If one were not aware of interference, one would argue that there were simply no em fields in these spatial regions).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that the existence of fermions i.e. particles which may not occupy the same quantum states, is due to out of phase (by π) interference. Interference already exists among $\exp(ipx)$ in a given eigenstate. There are two dimensions each with their own probability $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ together with the additional constraint that there is one particle at x i.e. the modulus squared of $\exp(ipx)$ is 1. If there are alternate $\exp(ipx)$ values e.g. $\exp(ip_1x)$, $\exp(ip_2x)$, probabilities add and the constraint is now a global one i.e. the particle

count is 1 if one integrates the modulus squared of the sum of $\exp(ipx)$'s with weights over all space.

There seems, however, to be an extra feature of interference that does not appear within a given eigenstate as it obeys a conservation of energy constraint at each x . One may form linear combinations of energy eigenstates and these may carry phase factors. In particular, one may have $W_a(x)+W_b(x)$ and $W_a(x)-W_b(x)$. Setting $a=b$ yields 0 for the second case. Thus, one has kind of out of phase by π (or alternate) interference which cancels the wavefunctions unless the two distinct energy states are occupied.

We extend this idea to that of two identical fermions i.e. $W_a(x_1)W_b(x_2)-W_a(x_2)W_b(x_1)$. Here $P(x_1,x_2)=P(x_2,x_1)$ so interchanging x_1 and x_2 in the wavefunction may only yield a phase e.g. -1 . The alternate phase interference which satisfies this local constraint, however, leads to the cancellation (by interference) of the entire wavefunction if $a=b$. This yields the fermion condition that only one fermion may occupy a specific quantum state. It follows from the same probability interference behaviour that exists among $\exp(ipx)$'s except that extra phases may appear as the constraint $P(x_1,x_2)=P(x_2,x_1)$ does not prevent this.

One may note that $W_a(x_1)W_b(x_2)-W_a(x_2)W_b(x_1)$ satisfies two constraints. First there is the local $P(x_1,x_2)=P(x_2,x_1)$ and then the global $\int dx_1 dx_2 W(x_1,x_2) = 2$ as there are two particles. For the case of $a=b$, the local constraint enforces that the two particles cancel each other out and the global constraint does not hold. The two particles cannot vanish, so they cannot occupy the same quantum state.

References

1. Kaplan, I. Pauli Principle and its Theoretical Foundation (2018 or later)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/1902.00499.pdf>